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EFFECTS OF LECTURERS STRESS AND BURNOUT ON THEIR ATTITUDE AND WORK PERFORMANCE IN HAKMAH THEOLOGICAL COLLEGE IN KALTUNGO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF GOMBE STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effects of lectures stress and burnout on their attitude and work performance (lecturing) in Hakmah Theological College Kaltungo, Gombe State, Nigeria. The research aimed to assess the prevalence of stress among the lecturers, examine its various effects on working (lecturing) performance, and strategies that the Institution administrators should implement to prevent Lecturers burnout. A descriptive survey design was used, data were gathered through self-constructed questionnaires and interviews. The sample size of the study consisted of 50 lecturers from the various departments in the institutions. The findings revealed that a significant majority of lecturers acknowledging the influence of stress and burnout on their attitude and performance towards work delivery. This study illustrates the adverse effects reported by lectures, including lack of motivation from the management, low output, poor delivery of lectures, lack of concentration, lack of good study room, disorganization etc. Transactional model stress was use for this stidy. These outcomes underscore the urgent need for targeted interventions and support mechanisms to enhance lecturers' outputs, dedication, well-being and the overall quality of education in the institution. Implications for policymakers and educational institutions involve prioritizing lecturers well-being, implementing organizational support structures, and integrating stress management modules into professional development programs.

KEYWORDS: *Effect, Lecturers, Stress, Attitude, Burnout, Work. Performance*

INTRODUCTION

In the field of lecturing, the working performance of staffs (lecturers) plays an important role in developing, and improving

the academic outcomes of the students. Globally, research has underscored a significant link between lecturers' stress, and burnout on their attitude and effectiveness in

the classroom (Jackson & Rothmann, 2020; Pienaar & Van Wyk, 2019; Milner & Khoza, 2019). Kenny (2021) further emphasized that lecturing experience can serve as a determinant of extreme stress and burnout, suggesting that there exists a relationship between professional longevity and psychological well-being of staffs.

Anshel and Kaissidis (2022), in their study on coping strategies following stressful events, found that there is a relationship between stress, strain, and attitude burnout, highlighting the importance of coping strategies and social support. Their findings support the notion that the working environment, characterized by unity and understanding among colleagues, significantly impacts lecturers' ability to navigate and manage stress and burnout as a supportive atmosphere not only fosters well-being of the lecturers but also facilitates the integration of innovative ideas that can help enhance their service delivery.

Lecturers may develop negative, cynical attitudes toward students and colleagues, due to stress and burnout leading to emotional detachment and reduced efficiency as opined by Kotherja, (2022). To support new teachers in preventing burnout, it is essential to establish a structured process that includes mentorship and targeted programs. Ongoing professional development training should also be incorporated to enhance their resilience. By fostering a culture of collaboration among educators, particularly through the lens of social justice, we can empower teachers and create a culturally responsive team-building framework. It is important to recognize that teachers often manage multiple subjects, which can

contribute to burnout, compounded by challenges in time management related to lesson planning.

In Hakman theological college, the performance of students is a matter of paramount concern for institution, community, locality and the state at large. Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASSU, 2024) identifies a critical challenge in the education sector, attributing suboptimal student performance not to staffing issues but rather to lecturers lacking essential pedagogical skills. Maslach, Schaufeli, and Leiter (2018) asserted that overloaded lecturers may distance themselves emotionally and cognitively from their work, leading to exhaustion and an inability to proactively respond to students' needs.

This increased workload and the complex nature of the institute curriculum may heighten the likelihood of stress and burnout among the lecturers, further exacerbating the challenges on their working performance in the institution. Recognizing the need to address this issue, this study sought to investigate the effects of stress and burnout on their attitude and work performance in Hakmah theological college in Kaltungo local government area of Gombe state, Nigeria. The study aims to contribute valuable insights into the complex dynamics between lecturers' well-being, work performance, and their ability to enhance student output/outcomes in and outside the institution. By examining the specific challenges faced by the lecturers, the research hopes to provoke targeted interventions that can uplift the lecturing profession and, consequently, improve the educational

landscape in Kaltungo local government area of Gombe state.

- **Statement of the Problem**

Lecturers, like many individuals in demanding professions, grapple and suffer with stress and burnout, exacerbated by the significant time spent in the workplace (Locker, 2020). This phenomenon is particularly pronounced in the lecturing profession, where lecturers face the dual challenge of maintaining classroom discipline and managing an overwhelming workload, leading to emotional exhaustion (Kokkinos, 2019). The complexities of a rapidly evolving and technologically driven society further contribute to lecturers' burnout, impacting on their overall performance (Okumbe, 2023). Despite the critical and supportive role of lecturers in shaping the future of the students, the specific dynamics of work-related stress and burnout among the undergraduate students of Hakmah theological college in Kaltungo remain understudied. The consequences of lecturer burnout extend beyond personal well-being, affecting lecture enthusiasm, engagement, and ultimately compromising their capacity to meet students' needs (Wentzel, 2021). Notably, variations in academic performance among schools in the region prompted the question; are these differences linked to lecturers' stress and burnout? Addressing this knowledge gap is crucial for understanding the factors influencing lecturers' well-being and working performance, facilitating the development of targeted interventions to support educators.

- **Aim and Objective of the Study**

The general aim of this study was to establish the effects of stress and burnout on lecturers' attitude and work performance in Hakmah theological college in Kaltungo local government area of Gombe state. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

- i. Establish the levels of stress and burnout among lecturers in Hakmah theological college.
- ii. Determine the effects of stress and burnout on the attitude and work performance of lecturers in their lecturing tasks in the institution.
- iii. To find and suggest some possible solution on the effects of stress and burnout on the attitude and work performance of lecturers in their lecturing tasks in the institution.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

- **The Concept of Stress, Burnout and Lecturers Attitude**

- **Stress**

Stress and burnout in the context of lecturing are well-established phenomena with far-reaching implications for lecturers' well-being and professional efficacy. Scholars have extensively examined the various dimensions of stress within the teaching profession, characterizing it as a complex interplay of external pressures and internal responses (Lonser, 2021). Defined as the body's physiological and psychological response to demands exceeding one's resources (Lazarus & Folkman, 2018), stress manifests uniquely for educators due to the diverse nature of their roles.

➤ **Burnout**

Burnout, often considered an advanced stage of chronic stress, is a prevailing concern in the education profession (Maslach & Leiter, 2018). It is described as a state of prolonged physical and emotional exhaustion resulting from continuous exposure to stressors in the workplace (Edu-Valsania, Laguia&Moriano, 2022). The educational context, marked by high demands and responsibilities, amplifies the likelihood of burnout among educators (Arvidsson, Leo, Larsson, et al., 2019). Researchers emphasize burnout as a gradual process, indicating a gradual erosion of passion and commitment to the educational profession over time (García-Rivera, Mendoza-Martínez & García-Alcaraz et al., 2022).

➤ **Lecturers Burnout**

Lecturer burnout, also known as academic burnout, refers to a state of emotional, mental, and physical exhaustion experienced by lecturers or academics, often resulting from prolonged stress, pressure, and lack of balance in their work life. According to Maslach and Leiter (2024), burnout is a psychological syndrome characterized by feelings of energy depletion, reduced professional efficacy, and cynicism or depersonalization.

Lecturer Burnout (often studied within the broader framework of academic burnout) refers to a state of chronic physical and emotional exhaustion, depersonalization (cynicism or detached attitude toward work and students), and reduced personal accomplishment experienced by university or college lecturers. It specifically manifests as negative, indifferent, or cynical attitudes

toward teaching, research, services/ duties, and interactions with students and colleagues. This syndrome arises from prolonged exposure to occupational stressors in higher education.

To gain a deeper understanding of the concept of stress and burnout in education, it is essential to explore the psychological and emotional aspects associated with these phenomena. A study by Hakanen, Bakker and Schaufeli (2019) highlighted the psychological strain experienced by teachers, emphasizing the link between excessive job demands and the manifestation of stress symptoms. Additionally, emotional exhaustion, a key component of burnout, has been identified as a critical factor influencing teacher attrition and job dissatisfaction (Ingersoll & Strong, 2017; Maslach & Leiter, 2021).

➤ **Work Stress**

Workplace stress is a common problem that has been well researched in a number of disciplines, including psychology, organizational behavior, and occupational health. Workplace stress is a complicated problem that has an enormous effect on both people and companies. The well-being of employees and organizational outcomes must be improved by comprehending the origin and effects of work stress and putting into practice efficient management and prevention techniques. Work stress can be defined as the harmful physical and emotional responses that occur when the requirements of the job do not match the capabilities, resources, or needs of the worker. It is a common phenomenon in many workplaces and can have negative effects on

employee health, job satisfaction, and productivity.

According to a study by Lee and Ashforth, (2022) work stress can be caused by a variety of factors including job demands, lack of control over the work environment, interpersonal conflicts, and role ambiguity. These factors can lead to emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment, which are all symptoms of burnout. In addition, prolonged exposure to work stress can increase the risk of developing physical health problems such as cardiovascular disease, musculoskeletal disorders, and lots more. For example, the job demand-control model proposes that increasing job control (i.e., the amount of discretion and decision-making power an employee has in their work) can help reduce work stress. Other strategies include social support from colleagues and supervisors and relaxation techniques such as deep breathing and meditation (Van Dijk et al., 2021).

Work stress is a common and potentially harmful phenomenon in the workplace. It can have negative effects on both employee health and organizational productivity. Employers should take steps to reduce work stress, such as providing social support and increasing job control, in order to create a healthy and productive work environment. Work stress among university lecturers is a growing concern as it has been found to have negative effects on their physical and mental health, as well as their job performance and satisfaction. A study by Aina and Adeleke revealed that university lecturers in Nigeria experience high levels of work stress due to factors such as workload, lack of support from colleagues and supervisors, and

inadequate compensation. Another study by Maslach and Leiter found that work stress among university lecturers is also influenced by the work environment, job insecurity, and the pressure to publish research. The consequences of work stress on university lecturers can be severe. A study by Osibanjo, et al. found that work stress can lead to burnout, depression, and other mental health issues among university lecturers. The study also found that work stress negatively affects job satisfaction and commitment, as well as the quality of teaching.

To address the issue of work stress among university lecturers, organizations can implement stress management programs and provide support to lecturers. A study by Yusoff, et al., found that stress management programs can significantly reduce work stress among university lecturers. Providing support, such as mentoring programs and professional development opportunities, can also help to reduce work stress by providing resources for coping and enhancing job satisfaction. Providing resources for coping and enhancing job satisfaction. Work stress among university lecturers is a significant issue that needs to be addressed to promote their well-being and job performance. It is essential for organizations to implement stress management programs and provide support to reduce work stress among lecturers.

- **Sources of Stress and Burnout**

Lecturers in Hakmah do encounter a myriad of stressors emanating from their professional responsibilities. The sources of stress and burnout among lecturers are varied, stemming from the diverse nature of their professional responsibilities. A

considerable body of literature underscores the diverse stressors that educators contend with in their daily roles. High workload is consistently identified as a primary stressor in the teaching profession (Arbia, Carbone, Stanzone & Szpunar, 2023). The pressure to cover curriculum requirements, prepare engaging lessons handout, and assess student performance in their theses/projects creates a demanding work environment that can lead to heightened stress levels. Administrative pressures also significantly contribute to lectures stress and burnout (Wanyonyi & Ouda, 2019).

The bureaucratic aspects of education, such as paperwork, documentation, and compliance with policies, can be time-consuming and mentally tasking for lecturers. These administrative demands divert lecturers focus from instructional activities, contributing to heightened stress and diminishing overall job satisfaction. Moreover, time constraints pose a pervasive challenge for educators (Hakanen et al., 2016). The need to balance teaching responsibilities, grading, and lesson planning within limited time frames places additional strain on educators. This constant juggling, can result in feelings of overwhelm and exhaustion, further exacerbating the risk of burnout.

In addition to internal pressures, lecturers grapple with external challenges related to maintaining classroom discipline and managing student behaviors (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2021). The challenging roles of handling diverse student personalities, addressing disciplinary issues, and ensuring a positive learning environment add emotional and psychological burdens to

teachers. The dynamic nature of the educational landscape, marked by societal expectations and technological advancements, introduces new stress elements into teaching (Khadka & Khadka, 2023). The pressure to adapt instructional methods to meet evolving educational standards, coupled with the integration of technology into the classroom, can lead to feelings of inadequacy and professional strain (Gibson & Dembo, 2020). It therefore implies that teachers face a confluence of stressors arising from their professional duties. Increased workload, administrative pressures, time constraints, classroom management challenges, and the evolving educational landscape collectively contribute to the complex web of stress and burnout within the lecturing profession.

- **Effects of Stress and Burnout in Relation to Lecturers' Work Performance**

- **Physical/Physiological effects**

The physical toll of stress and burnout on lecturers has been extensively examined in literatures. Chronic stress has been linked to adverse health outcomes, including heightened levels of corticosteroids, commonly referred to as the stress hormone (American Psychological Association, 2024). Prolonged exposure to elevated corticosteroids levels can lead to fatigue, sleep disturbances, and compromised immune function, all of which impact teachers' overall physical well-being (Bellingrath, Weigl & Kudielka, 2023). In addition, studies have explored the

physiological effects of burnout, revealing a correlation between emotional exhaustion and cardiovascular issues (Dimsdale, 2023). This connection underscores the severe implications of burnout on lecturers' health, emphasizing the need for interventions to mitigate these physical repercussions.

➤ **Behavioral/relational effects**

Behavioral and relational dynamics are significantly influenced by lecturers' experiences of stress and burnout. Lecturers experiencing burnout often exhibit increased absenteeism and decreased job commitment (Maslach & Leiter, 2021). The erosion of commitment is reflected in reduced engagement with colleagues and diminished participation in collaborative efforts (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2021). Additionally, cynicism and emotional withdrawal become prominent behavioral manifestations, negatively impacting teacher-student relationships and the overall classroom environment (Maslach et al., 2021).

➤ **Emotional and psychological effects**

Emotionally and psychologically, the impact of stress and burnout on lecturers is profound. A study by Ingersoll and Strong (2020) highlighted the emotional exhaustion experienced by lecturers, emphasizing the connection between excessive job demands and the manifestation of stress symptoms. Burnout is associated with diminished job

satisfaction, heightened feelings of cynicism, and a reduced sense of personal accomplishment (Maslach et al., 2021). These emotional and psychological effects contribute to an overall decline in lecturers' mental well-being and job performance. The erosion of lecturers' enthusiasm and engagement further undermines their capacity to meet students' needs (Wentzel, 2016). Notably, this decline in performance is not limited to the academic realm; it extends to co-curricular activities and overall school climate.

• **Strategies Institution administrators should implement to prevent Lecturers burnout**

Preventing lectures burnout requires proactive and systemic strategies that address the emotional, professional, and logistical challenges teachers face daily. Based on the administrator's insights, current efforts to support educators and students are limited but evolving. While some initiatives are in place, there remains significant room for improvement (Administrator; A personal communication, November 29, 2025).

The administrator emphasized that there is currently no formal training for recognizing and addressing teacher burnout. Instead, the process is "more intuitive," relying on administrators' personal awareness and relationships with staff.

The message to lecturers is clear: *"You have to take care of yourselves because the work will always be there. While*

well-meaning, this approach places the burden of self-care primarily on lecturers, without offering concrete systems of support".

This gap highlights the need for structured training programs to equip administrators with the skills to identify and mitigate burnout early.

For students, the school has implemented restorative justice practices and school counseling services.

These initiatives foster a culture of respect and empathy, encouraging students to "treat others how you want to be treated." However, similar programs are notably absent for teachers. The administrator acknowledged that while human resources provide access to psychological services through benefits packages, there are no dedicated counseling or wellness programs for staff. This disparity suggests a critical need for schools to extend mental health resources to educators, ensuring they receive the same level of care provided to students.

The administrator identified several long-term changes essential for addressing lecturers' burnout:

1. Create Time for Planning and Rest:

Lecturers should have dedicated time for planning and relaxation which is a practical solution. This approach would reduce the day-to-day stress on teachers, enabling them to focus on delivering high-quality instruction.

2. Increased Mental Health Support: The administrator proposed having a full-time

psychologist in every school and increasing the availability of counselors. These professionals could provide direct support to both students and teachers, addressing mental health challenges before they escalate.

3. Recess Monitors: Hiring recess monitors to engage students in positive play could alleviate some of the supervisory responsibilities of teachers, allowing them to recharge during breaks.

These systemic changes reflect a recognition that addressing teacher burnout requires rethinking how schools allocate resources and prioritize staff well-being.

Implementing these strategies could have a profound impact on student outcomes.

Research consistently shows that lecturers well-being is directly linked to classroom quality and student achievement (Braun, Schonert-Reichl, & Roeser, 2020). When lecturers are given the time and resources to manage their workloads and mental health, they can create more engaging and supportive learning environments. This, in turn, fosters greater student motivation, improved behavior, and higher academic performance. Furthermore, expanding mental health resources for teachers could reduce absenteeism and output, ensuring that students experience consistent and high-quality instruction. Restorative justice practices and positive play supervision would also help cultivate a school culture that prioritizes emotional well-being, reinforcing the connection between lecturers and student success.

While the administrator's proposals are promising, the lack of current programs for lecturers highlights a systemic issue. To fully address burnout, schools must invest in professional development for administrators, equipping them with tools to recognize and respond to early signs of lecturers' stress. Comprehensive wellness programs, including mindfulness training, peer support groups, and accessible on-site counseling would complement these efforts and create a more resilient workforce. By prioritizing lecturers' well-being through dedicated planning time, mental health resources, and reduced supervisory responsibilities, schools can create a supportive environment that benefits both educators and students. However, to truly address burnout, schools must close the existing gaps in training and resources, ensuring that all staff members are equipped to thrive.

- **How can lecturers manage their lecturing and learning responsibilities to prevent burnout and ensure a positive impact on their students' educational experiences?**

Teachers play a critical role in shaping their students' educational experiences, and managing their responsibilities effectively are essential to prevent burnout and maintain a positive classroom environment. Insights from interviews with teachers and a school psychologist, alongside supporting research, highlight practical strategies to address this challenge.

One of the key ways' teachers can manage their responsibilities is by fostering strong professional relationships with colleagues.

A lecturer emphasized the importance of collaborative planning with colleagues teaching the same grade level, as it distributes workload and creates a shared sense of responsibility. "Three minds are better than one," he also highlighting that teamwork not only reduces individual stress but also leads to higher-quality lessons (November 29, 2025).

Another lecturer added that, some lecturers echoed that strong relationships among educators "lead to a supportive work environment" where resources and strategies can be shared, enabling teachers to feel valued and appreciated (November 29, 2025). This collaborative approach enhances both teacher well-being and student outcomes by fostering cohesive lesson delivery and reducing classroom stress.

Several lecturers emphasized the importance of setting boundaries and prioritizing self-care.

A lecturers recommended leaving work at school and not taking it home, allowing for personal time to recharge. This sentiment was echoed by (November 29, 2025)., who shared the value of prioritizing family and taking "mental health days" to reset after periods of overstimulation.

Research supports this, as Kharbach (2024) found that effective time management and personal reflection are crucial for maintaining a healthy work-life balance and preventing burnout.

Lecturers can also manage stress by fostering a positive atmosphere in their classrooms.

A senior lecturer highlighted the importance of projecting positivity and enthusiasm, even on challenging days, to encourage students to stay engaged and motivated (*November 30, 2025*). This strategy aligns with the findings of Braun, Schonert-Reichl, and Roeser (2020), who noted that teachers who effectively regulate their emotions create more supportive and productive learning environments, positively impacting student well-being and academic success.

Additionally, the school psychologist emphasized that students are highly sensitive to their lecturer emotional states. When lecturers appear stressed or disengaged, students often mirror this behavior, leading to decreased motivation and classroom disruptions (*November 29, 2025*). He suggested integrating social-emotional learning (SEL) practices not just for students but also for the lecturers. Planning better and engaging in SEL practices helps create a calmer classroom environment, which benefits both teachers and students. This is supported by research findings by Shen et al. (2020), which found that teachers who engage in social-emotional strategies are better equipped to manage classroom challenges and maintain student motivation.

- **Theoretical Framework**

Lazarus and Folkman's 1984 Transactional Model of Stress and Coping posits that stress isn't just an external event but a dynamic interaction (transaction) between a person and their environment, focusing on cognitive appraisals (Primary: Is it a threat/challenge? Secondary: Can I cope?) and coping

strategies (problem-focused vs. emotion-focused), influencing well-being through a continuous cycle of appraisal, coping, and reappraisal. Stress arises from perceived demands exceeding resources, highlighting the subjective interpretation of stressors, not just the stressors themselves.

Stress management includes a range of methods that can help individuals cope with stress and improve overall well-being, although results can vary depending on the person or situation. It also consists of a wide spectrum of techniques and psychotherapies aimed at controlling a person's level of psychological stress, especially chronic stress, generally for the purpose of improving the function of everyday life. Stress produces numerous physical and mental symptoms which vary according to each individual's situational factors. These can include a decline in physical health, such as headaches, chest pain, fatigue, sleep problems, and depression. The process of stress management is a key factor that can lead to a happy and successful life in modern society. Stress management provides numerous ways to manage anxiety and maintain overall well-being.

There are several models of stress management, each with distinctive explanations of mechanisms for controlling stress. More research is necessary to provide a better understanding of which mechanisms actually operate and are effective in practice. In Hakman theological college, this theory is very reverent because the staff of the college has to crosscheck wither the work that they will be taken is either right or wrong, how effective it is on their health and their emotional stability.

METHODOLOGY

- **Research design**

The study utilized a descriptive survey design to collect research data. This research approach, as outlined by Denscombe (1998), is designed to offer a snapshot of a specific situation at a given time. Unlike experimental designs, survey research does not aim to manipulate variables or control conditions (Kelley, Clark, Brown & Sitzia, 2003). Given that the events or conditions being studied have already occurred, the researcher selects pertinent variables for the analysis of their relationships. The independent variables included physical complications, emotional exhaustion, behavioural disorders and changes in thinking process. The primary focus was to ascertain how these factors influenced lectures work performance. The dependent variables, reflecting aspects of lecturers working performance such as emotions, drug and substance abuse, motivation, anxiety, and concentration, were determined through the lens of stress and burnout.

- **Location of the study**

The research was conducted in Hakmah Theological College Kaltungo, situated within Kaltungo Local Government Area of Gombe state.

- **Target population and sample size**

The target group was all the lecturers in the institution. The study targeted 50 lecturers of Hakmah theological college. From this population, stratified random sampling was used to select a sample of 50 lecturers.

- **Data Collection and Analysis**

The primary instrument employed for data collection was in-depth interview. This method facilitated the collection of primary

data on lecturers' stress levels and their underlying causes. These interviews were exclusively conducted to the lectures and HODs in the institution, as they possessed crucial information not possible to entirely capture using the questionnaire. Face-to-face interviews allowed for in-depth exploration of aspects such as lecturers performance and motivational factors.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

- **Levels of lecturers' stress and lecturers attitude burnout**

The first goal of this study was to establish the levels of stress and burnout among lecturers in Hakman theological college in Kaltungo LGA of Gombe state. As it turned out, majority (91.9%) of the lecturers agreed that they had experienced a lot of stress which led them to attitudinal burnout in their place of work, while (8.1%) indicated that they had not experienced stress or burnout in their place of work. Interviews with a department HOD revealed that, majority (85%,) were of the view that stress and burnout were experienced at their place of work sometimes due to some factors while (10%) indicated that stress and burnout were experienced at their place of work on more frequent levels. These findings reveal a significant concern regarding the prevalence of stress and burnout among the lecturers in Hakmah theological college, with 5% of respondents acknowledging their experience of these challenges. This finding underscores the pervasive nature of stress and burnout within the lecturing profession and necessitates a thoughtful examination of its implications. Previous research aligns with these findings, emphasizing that the lecturing profession is

particularly susceptible to high levels of stress and burnout (Kyriacou, 2019; Maslach et al., 2020). The impact of stress on teacher well-being has been a consistent theme in educational research, with studies highlighting its association with reduced job satisfaction, increased absenteeism, and compromised effectiveness in the.

The acknowledgment of stress and burnout among lectures in this study raises concerns about its potential influence on the quality of education delivered. Past research has demonstrated a link between staffs' burnout and diminished instructional quality, ultimately impacting student outcomes (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2021). This suggests that addressing lecturers' well-being is not merely an individual concern but has broader implications for the overall educational landscape. The results of this study also highlight the need for organizational support and interventions to mitigate stress and burnout among lecturers. This aligns with existing literature that emphasized the importance of creating a supportive work environment, providing mental health resources, and implementing stress reduction strategies (Travers & Cooper, 2013; Maslach & Leiter, 2021). Additionally, professional development programs should be reevaluated to incorporate modules on stress management and coping strategies, aligning with research that underscores the role of ongoing training in educators' well-being.

On the effects of lecturers' stress and burnout on their work performance, the study sought to establish the effects of stress on lecturers' lecturing task in Hakmah theological college. It emerged from the study that majority of the teachers (86.3%) agreed that stress and

burnout influenced their performance as lecturers. Another (12.7%) indicated that stress and burnout did not influence their working performance. This significant agreement among teachers underscores the pervasive nature of stress and burnout within the lecturing profession and its palpable effects on their ability to carry out lecturing responsibilities effectively. The results agree with existing literature that emphasizes the interconnectedness between lecturers' well-being and their working performance. Previous studies have demonstrated that high levels of stress and burnout can lead to reduced job satisfaction, diminished instructional quality, and compromised effectiveness in the classroom (Kyriacou, 2019). The current study's alignment with these established trends reinforces the urgency of addressing stress-related challenges among lecturers to ensure optimal educational outcomes in Hakman theological college. The implications extend beyond individual teachers to impact the broader educational landscape, emphasizing the imperative for targeted interventions and support mechanisms to enhance lecturers' well-being and, by extension, the quality of education provided in the region.

The lectures indicated that stress and burnout affected their performance in various ways. The results imply that stress and burnout had numerous adverse effects on lecturers contributing to their dismal performance in their lecturing and other roles including making them feel demotivated, lack concentration, get disorganized and hence the poor delivery in class. The finding that 27.3% of the lecturers reported that stress and burnout led to low work output aligns with

previous research that has consistently demonstrated a negative correlation between elevated stress levels and reduced productivity among lecturers (Hakanen et al., 2018).

Furthermore, 23.9% of lectures reported experiencing poor delivery in class due to stress and burnout.

This echoes the broader literature that underscores the detrimental impact of burnout on instructional quality, with burned-out teachers struggling to maintain effective teaching practices (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2021).

The reported demotivation by 23.3% of lectures is consistent with studies highlighting the link between stress, burnout, and diminished motivation in the teaching profession (Maslach et al., 2019).

The results also show that there were 17.6% of lecturers who indicated a lack of concentration as a consequence of stress and burnout. This finding corresponds with existing research that associates burnout with cognitive impairments, potentially hindering lectures' ability to focus and engage effectively in their professional duties (Kyriacou, 2019). The reported disorganization by 4% of teachers aligns with studies emphasizing the disruptive effects of stress on organizational skills and task management (Maslach & Leiter, 2019). Interestingly, a small proportion (2.2%) of teachers expressed that stress prompted them to work even more, while 1.7% felt under pressure to work. These findings suggest varied coping mechanisms among lecturers, with some responding to stress by intensifying their efforts. The varied responses by teachers underscore the

complex nature of stress and burnout in the lecturing profession, with individual lecturer employing diverse strategies to navigate the challenges they face (Ingersoll & Strong, 2021).

• How stress and burnout affected Lecturers working performance

Effects of stress and burnout	No. of Lecturers	Percent
Low output/performance	15	30.0
Poor delivery in class	9	18.0
Feeling demotivated	11	22.0
Lack of concentration	7	14.0
Being disorganized	5	10.0
Feeling under pressure to work	3	6.0
Total	50	100%

CONCLUSION

This study shed light on the significant impact of lecturers' stress and burnout on lecturers in Hakmah theological college Kaltungo LGA. The findings reveal a concerning prevalence of stress and burnout among lecturers, with a majority acknowledging its influence on their work performance. The adverse effects reported by lecturers, including low output, poor delivery in class, demotivation, lack of concentration, and disorganization, underscore the pressing

need for interventions to address the challenges faced by educators in this region. The implications of these findings extend beyond individual lecturers to the broader educational landscape. High levels of stress and burnout among lecturers can compromise the quality of education delivered, impacting student outcomes and overall educational effectiveness. Policymakers and educational institutions should prioritize the well-being of lecturers, recognizing it as integral to the success of the education system. To address these challenges, interventions should encompass organizational support, targeted professional development, and policies that prioritize lecturers' well-being. Creating a supportive work environment, offering mental health resources, and implementing stress reduction strategies are essential steps toward fostering a healthier lecturing community. Professional development programs should incorporate modules on stress management and coping strategies to empower lecturers with the skills to navigate the challenges of their profession effectively. The study also underscores the need for ongoing research to delve deeper into the specific causes and manifestations of stress and burnout among lecturers in Hakman theological college. Long-term interventions informed by empirical evidence can contribute to sustained improvements in lecturers' well-being and, consequently, the overall quality of education in the region.

- **Recommendation**

- i. The school management should be given incentives that will motivate the lecturers to do more.

- ii. The lecturers should set boundaries between their personal activities and the academic work.

- iii. Self-care and exercises should be done to reduce stress.

- iv. Lecturers should learn to control their emotions, not to take family issues to the place of work.

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